

A Magnetised High-Pressure Gaseous Argon TPC for the DUNE Near Detector

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on behalf of the DUNE collaboration

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INDIANA UNIVERSITY

Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment

- Wide-band **high-intensity** (anti)neutrino beam produced at Fermilab
- **Near detector (ND)** complex to control **systematic uncertainties**
- **70-kt liquid argon far detector (FD)** 1.5km underground in the South Dakota

Neutrino mass hierarchy
Leptonic CP violation
Test PMNS paradigm

Supernova neutrinos
Solar neutrinos

Proton decay
Inelastic Dark Matter

Oscillations

Astrophysics

BSM

Phases of DUNE

Parameter	Phase I	Phase II
FD mass	20 kt fiducial	40 kt fiducial
Beam power	up to 1.2 MW	2.4 MW
ND config.	ND-LAr, TMS, SAND	ND-LAr, ND-GAr, SAND

- DUNE will be built using a **staged approach**
- Phase I is sufficient for early physics goals, i.e. mass ordering
- **Phase II necessary** to unlock full physics potential
 - Determine leptonic CP violation over a range of values
 - Resolve mixing parameter degeneracies

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See the impact of the ND upgrade!

Near Detector complex

You are here!

- Main goal: **measure** beam rate to predict unoscillated **event rates** at the FD
- **Constrain systematic uncertainties** for oscillation measurement
- Independent physics programme — **cross sections and BSM**

True for both Phase I and II

Near Detector complex

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ND-GAr concept

- **Primary goal:** neutrino interaction and detector acceptance **systematics**
- A magnetised detector, with an **argon-rich HPgTPC** and a **calorimeter**
- Old ND-GAr **design predates** DUNE two **phases** approach
 - We are **re-evaluating detector parameters**, driven by Phase II **physics** requirements
 - Exploring **new technologies** and cost-effective options

4π acceptance	Sign selection
PID	Momentum resolution
Low thresholds	Volume density ratio

Key features

Role of ND-GAr

- Track muons exiting ND-LAr — measure the ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ spectra
- Measure neutrino interactions with **kinematic acceptance similar to FD** — constrain systematics not accessible to ND-LAr
- Characterise **pion energy spectrum** in ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ CC interactions — FSI expected to have significant impact at low energies

Interaction systematics

- Addressing neutrino interaction systematics requires resolving **discrepancies between interaction models**
- The HPgTPC gives DUNE **access to low-energy** hadrons below LAr thresholds, where models often disagree

- **Leading systematic in neutrino experiments — final state interactions (FSI)**

- Re-interactions of hadrons as they travel through the nucleus

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Particle identification

- ND-GAr can combine its subsystems for robust PID decisions

Proton / MIP separation w/
HPgTPC calorimetry

Muon / pion classification w/
ECal (and MuID)

Neutral particle reconstruction
w/ ECal

HPgTPC charge readout

- Multi-wire proportional chambers use layers of anode and cathode **wires** to **amplify signal**
 - Electrons drift to anode wires, avalanche multiplication near wire
- Current: Gas Electron Multipliers and **sequential amplification** stages
 - Electrons passing through ~ 70 μm holes in GEM foils are accelerated by high-intensity electric field

[Nucl.Instrum.Meth.A 622 \(2010\) 316-367](#)

[Nucl.Instrum.Meth.A 805 \(2016\) 2-24](#)

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R&D — Multi-Wire Chambers

- US-led (GOAT) and UK-led (TOAD) test stands completed **pressure scans** using ALICE inner / outer MWPCs
- Able to **maintain gain** at high pressure increasing voltage

TOAD @ RHUL

GOAT @ FNAL

R&D — Gas Electron Multipliers

- Ongoing **testing** with different **reference gases** with GORG* @ FNAL
- Define **optimised GEM parameters** for a larger triple-GEM structure for use in a test beam
- Gain **simulation studies** used to guide and compare results

* Persian for wolf

R&D — Gas Electron Multipliers

GORG @ FNAL

- Last August GORG chamber was placed inside GOAT pressure vessel for **first high-pressure operations**
- Performed **gain scans** from 1 atm to 3.4 atm

Log-linear dependence,
suppression at higher
pressures

- Next steps:
 - **Polarise GEM foils independently**
 - **Integration with FPGA-based readout**
 - **New pressure vessel for tests beam**

Summary

- ND-GAr is a **key component of DUNE**, needed to constrain systematics and full physics potential
- A wide range of physics and detector R&D studies are underway to **define the design of ND-GAr**
 - Tailoring detector parameters to **fit the physics requirements** of Phase II
- Lessons learned from **R&D** with MWPCs, now focusing on **GEMs** as primary candidate for charge readout
- Aim for TDR in late 2020s, finish construction in mid 2030s

Backup slides

Low energy hadrons — GAr vs LAr

ν_μ CC 7 proton event in a ND-GAr

Same event in a LArTPC

BSM opportunities

Credit K. Kelly

- ND-GAr is a very capable **BSM machine**
- Perfect for searches looking for **decay signatures**
 - **Signals** increase with **volume**, **background** scales with **density**
- **Explored sensitivity** to different BSM scenarios
 - HNLs, ALPs, tridents, ...
- **Collaboration** between experimentalists and theorists

[Eur.Phys.J.C 81 \(2021\) 1, 78](#)

R&D — Readout electronics

- TOAD full slice **test of readout electronics** at high pressure
 - **FPGA-based readout** solution optimised for low-occupancy detectors
 - Multiple SAMPA ASICs mounted per FEC make **cost-effective** option

[arXiv:2507.17425](https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.17425) (accepted in JINST)

FEC board with 2 SAMPA chips

SNR map @ 5 bar

- System keeps **noise low** enough for target MeV-scale physics
 - Compensates for gain decrease due to higher density
- Readout works with either MWPCs or GEMs

R&D — GEMs next steps

- **Polarise** GEM foils **independently**, increase parameter dimensionality
- Working on extending **dynamic range** of readout
- Preparing for GEM-SAMPA readout **integration**
- **New pressure vessel** being procured for **neutron beam tests**

New lab space @ IU

Goal: medium-scale
GEM-based prototype

